

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SOCIAL BUSINESS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN GEORGIA, CHALLENGES AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

Zhozhushvili N.

Doctor of Economic sciences

Associate Professor of The Gori State University

Abstract

Climate change and endless wars in the modern world have increased the importance of sustainable development of society. The business community has become one of the main players in creating a future that will help overcome the challenges faced by the states and ensure the creation of a system for society and the world as a whole, which, taking into account the interests of the economic development and environmental protection of the society, ensures human well-being and the increase in the quality of life. Many firms are keenly monitoring the impact of their activities on the environment and implementing various environmental, social, and corporate governance (ESG) standards, known as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Social business, together with the state, is an auxiliary force on the way to achieving sustainable goals. Not only do they think about financial benefits, but they also have a positive social and environmental impact on society and the world, which sets them apart from traditional businesses. They contribute to the creation of innovative technologies and approaches. In different countries of the world, including Georgia, many social impact enterprises are already facing certain challenges. The paper aims to determine the importance of social enterprise activities and to analyze and evaluate existing problems.

Keywords: social business, sustainability, challenges, economic development, social responsibility.

Introduction

Sustainability in the business field is defined by the strategy of the company to reduce the negative impact on the environment caused by their operations in a product market. An organization's sustainability practices are commonly analyzed in terms of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) metrics. Because of the global warming problems, social business is becoming more and more popular. The existence of such organizations has a positive impact not only on a community but also on a region and the world. All of these contribute to the formation of a sustainable society. In addition, social business is actively gaining a place in Transcaucasia and the world. Social business in Georgia has been attracting attention since 2010. The terms "social business" and "social entrepreneurship" do not exist in the legislation of Georgia. Additionally, there is no specific definition of what role and functions such an enterprise should perform. Because of this, it is difficult to find out which enterprise is social and which is not. Business organizations themselves try to gain recognition of the status of social business in society. Because of all these issues mentioned, social business is facing some challenges in Georgia.

The purpose of this article is to determine the features of social business, to analyze the challenges they have to face, and to assess the relevance of social business for sustainable development.

For this purpose, the following methods are used in the paper, such as desk **research methods** (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, or other techniques) as well as statistical methods (grouping, graphical or tabular representation, and others). A survey of question-and-answer methods was also done, as well as quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Literature Review

The research results related to social business are used in this paper. In addition, the literature includes English-language studies and official websites of existing social enterprises.

„Social entrepreneurship and youth” - October, 2022. The research done by Ipsos European Public Affairs. The survey is coordinated by the European Commission's director-general for Communications. (DG COMM "Media monitoring and Eurobarometer" department). Ipsos European Public Affairs surveyed young people aged from 15 to 30, in 27 European Union (EU) countries. 25,992 young people were interviewed via Computer Assisted Web Interviews (CAWI) using Ipsos online panels and their partner network.

„The research on the impact of Social Enterprises in Georgia” - Tbilisi, 2022. "Institute of Social Research and Analysis" commissioned by "The Center for Strategic Research and Development of Georgia (CSR DG)" - the given document includes research on the impact of enterprises, which was held in Georgia. This specific research represents the results of the study of the existing enterprises operating in Georgia. The studies in this guide confirm the social existence of challenges facing businesses. Besides, there is also a study about the results and impact of the pandemic, how it impacted the social business, and the importance of these challenges on the social business.

„Building Social Business: A New Kind of Capitalism That Serves Humanity's Most Urgent Needs” – Muhammad Yunus, 2011. The book describes the first steps taken by the author in pursuing social business, to solve social problems.

„Korea Social Enterprise Promotion Agency”. 2020. Asia Social Economy Casebook- In this book social enterprises of Asia are included. There are goals

and challenges described that are facing them. The social business market of developed countries such as Singapore and Korea is also described.

Discussion of the Paper

Social Business concept was first created for poor countries context, but poverty is not a problem for only developing countries. The term "social business" was created by Nobel laureate Professor Muhammad Yunus. Muhammad Yunus, (born 28 June 1940, Chittagong, East Bengal, now Bangladesh), is a Bangladeshi economist and founder of Grameen Bank. The bank in question was an institution that provided microcredit (small loans to poor people with no collateral) to help clients build credit and maintain financial stability. Today, Grameen Bank has more than 8.4 million members, 97 percent of whom are women, and has disbursed more than \$12.5 billion in loans since its inception.¹ In 2006, the Norwegian Nobel Committee jointly awarded Muhammad Yunus and Grameen Bank with the Nobel Peace Prize for "Efforts in Economic and Social Development". According to him, a social business is a business that has a "primarily social vision." Social business is beyond the world and is only focused on the pursuit of profit. Its purpose is to solve social problems using business methods, including the creation and sale of products and services.²

The main purpose of social business is to solve social, economic, and environmental issues, which are affecting the world. Such as homelessness, hunger, illnesses, pollution, and low level of education.³ Compared to traditional business, social wealth creation moves to the forefront and becomes the main focus of activity and interest. Profitability is seen as a means to achieve this goal. Social business is 100% dedicated to solving human problems. A business that can solve human problems and also create wealth. Social enterprises are an important part of social business. Instead of turning a blind eye to problems in society and leaving it to the government or the business sector to solve them, social entrepreneurs seek new ideas, create new approaches, and come up with innovative solutions

In 2015, the member states of the United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which includes three areas: eradicating poverty, preventing inequality and addressing climate change, and sets 17 Sustainable Development Goals for a better future for people and the planet. Social businesses are very important for these goals and the economic development of the country because of their core values, which include: employment, jobs (long-term unemployed, disabled, homeless, at-risk youth, and gender-discriminated women), innovation (new goods and services), social capital (referred to as the set of resources, or values, associated with the possession of a network of long-term relationships between individuals) and

capital promotion. Social entrepreneurship helps create a fairer society by addressing social issues and their social mission, not just profit maximization.

Social needs are different in different parts of the world. And therefore, the solutions to these problems vary. In some cases, social business dramatically changes the economic situation of the country's population. It helps the representatives of the lowest social class to create basic living conditions, and ultimately to achieve economic sustainability. One of the first examples is the Grameen Bank created by Professor Muhammad Yunus. This microfinance organization has played a very important role in the process of economic empowerment in Bangladesh. Grameen Danone Foods Ltd (GDFL) is a joint venture between Grameen Group of Bangladesh and French conglomerate Groupe Danone. The company's goal was to provide nutritional yogurt (brand name Shokti doi) to nearly 50 million Bangladeshi children using an innovative social business model. Grameen Danone Foods (GDFL) was created to provide different types of nutrients, which are not included in the meals of rural children of Bangladesh.⁴

Social business is not only relatable in developing countries. It plays a big role in developed countries' economic and social development too. **South Korea** is a highly developed industrial country. In this country, the products of social enterprises have a special mark on the label, which makes them more attractive to Korean consumers. Korea has many social impact startups operating in the fields of social innovation, social change, and social entrepreneurship. This startups are dedicated to good cause, new strategies, concepts, and ideas.

Meeting social needs is also a priority in European countries. The European Union's policy to stimulate innovation among young people is committed to promoting the personal, social and professional development of young Europeans through their education, quality jobs, and the creation of opportunities. There are about 2.8 million social enterprises in Europe and they employ about 13.6 million people. In EU member states, the share of social economy in paid employment ranges from 0.6% to 9.9%. The European Commission, because of its important role, promotes social and inclusive entrepreneurship in job creation, work integration and inclusive and sustainable development. In 2022, Ipsos European Public Affairs surveyed 25,992 young people between the ages of 15 and 30 in the 27 member states of the European Union (EU). Across the EU, one in five respondents say that companies should try to maximize profits for their owners and shareholders and almost four in ten (37%) say that companies should try to put people and the planet before profit. The rest of the respondents (39%) chose a neutral position, which is quite thought-provoking.

¹ Yunus Funds -www.yunusfb.com

² by Muhammad Yunus. – May 10, 2011 „Building Social Business: The New Kind of Capitalism that Serves Humanity's Most Pressing Needs Paperback”

³ What is social business? HEC Paris. 2023 <https://www.hec.edu/en/faculty-research/centers/society-organizations-institute/think/so-institute-executive-factsheets/what-social-business>)

⁴ Rangan, V. Kasturi, and Katharine Lee. January 2016. "Grameen Danone Foods Ltd., a Social Business." Harvard Business School Case 511-025

From this survey a very interesting facts were displayed. Young people think that it is very important for the employer to have a social goals (75%) or environmental goals (73%) for the company; they also think that it is important for the company to have its' employees take part in decision making (78%). Nevertheless, 90% of young people are in favor of a good salary and benefits, 89% are in favor of maintaining a balance between work and life, 88% want to have a financially stable company, and 87% want to support their career development.⁵

65% of respondents in the Czech Republic and 85% in Malta and Portugal believe that "it is very important for a potential employer to define social goals". In the rest of the countries, the opinion was divided as follows: Bulgaria (40%), Cyprus (37%), Slovenia (36%), Greece, Malta and Romania (all 35%) and Luxembourg and Portugal (both 34%). The rest of the European Union countries this proportion is in between 17-31%. During the research, it was revealed that almost four out of every ten respondents (37%) think that an important reason preventing youth entrepreneurship is the lack of sufficient capital/resources for self-employment; A slightly smaller share (31%) refers to the lack of knowledge/education/skills in starting and managing a business. More than a third of respondents (36%) think that financial risks stop young people from becoming entrepreneurs. About half of the respondents think that the EU is making "some effort" (34%) or "a lot of effort" (14%) to reduce youth unemployment, while the other half think that the EU is making little effort in this direction. A similar picture emerges with the EU's efforts to support people who want to start their own businesses with a positive social impact. About half of the respondents answered that the European Union makes efforts to support social entrepreneurship, unfortunately, the other half does not feel this support.

⁵ Flash Eurobarometer 513 Social entrepreneurship and youth – October 2022, Summary. <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer>

Georgia is a country with a developing economy. Here, social business has been attracting attention since 2010. The terms "social business" and "social entrepreneurship" do not exist in the legislation of Georgia. In addition, it is not specifically defined what functions such an enterprise should perform. Because of this, it is difficult to know which enterprise is social and which is not. Business objects themselves are trying to get recognition of the status of social business in society. It is possible to engage in this activity as a non-entrepreneurial legal entity or a legal entity of private law. Benefits do not exist directly in the social enterprise. Also, there is no special agency to support social businesses only. According to the data of the Alliance of Social Enterprises of Georgia, 47 social enterprises are registered. In total, they have employed 453 people.⁶ They are representatives of different fields and regions. Representatives of traditional crafts are - 26%, service - 30%, household items and decoration - 15%, knowledge - 11%, environmental protection and natural products - 7-7%, and social service provision - 4%.

Although we do not have the meaning of social business in Georgian legislation. This type of business is still possible. It is possible to engage in this activity as a non-entrepreneurial legal entity or a legal entity of private law. A non-entrepreneurial (non-commercial) legal entity can carry out social entrepreneurship by establishing a separate entrepreneurial legal entity. Benefits do not exist directly on the social enterprise. It depends on the entrepreneur, within which organizational-legal form they will carry out their activities, and in this regard the existence of benefits is determined.

Social entrepreneurship is a relatively new sector in Georgia. Until today, the legislation in Georgia does not recognize the concept of social entrepreneurship, and it is not defined in any official document, nor is it recognized at the legislative or political level. Therefore, the organizations operating in this field interpret

⁶ Alliance of Social Enterprises of Georgia. 20.06. 2023 - <https://seageorgia.ge/ka/social-enterprises/10>

the mentioned concept independently based on the goals of the programs and taking into account the international experience. International organizations provide grants and financial support to enterprises. In 2018, only the law "On Social Entrepreneurship" was introduced in the Parliament. There are individual initiatives to support the sector at the national and local levels, although the existing practice is fragmented and has the form of individual cases. Examples of this are: "Children and Youth Development Fund" - 42 projects were financed through the fund in 2013-2016. It is worth noting that the Youth Agency - Social Entrepreneurship is no longer included in its regulations as a priority, but the development of entrepreneurial skills is their goal. There is only a note about social entrepreneurship in the document defining the government strategy given in "Basic data and directions of the coun-

try for the years 2019-2022". In particular, helping social enterprises with the help of the non-governmental sector and "facilitating the strengthening of youth ties".⁷ It is worth mentioning that individual municipalities of Georgia actively promote the development of social entrepreneurship through various financings at the local level.

Within the framework of the work, we conducted a study on the example of the Shida Kartli region, as a result of which about 300 respondents were interviewed. It was found that 58.3% of respondents have heard and partially know the importance of social business. 22.2% have heard and it is completely clear to them the importance of social business, 13.9% have heard, but they do not know its meaning, and the rest do not know what it represents. The research shows that the majority of the population already has little information about social business.⁸ Figure 1

Figure 1

It was also found from the same research that 57.1% of the respondents consider the social business and entrepreneurship development goal to improve the social condition of the population (mainly vulnerable groups, disabled people), 20% to develop the business sector, 33.9% to support the development of innovative ideas. Most of them said that they would buy the product if it had a label stating that it was a product of social business.

The goals of social businesses of Georgia includes overcoming poverty and employment. These are the main social objective of the enterprise, followed by the provision of social services, education and promotion of vulnerable groups are equally expressed. The lowest rate is for traditional craft, craft preservation and development, and environmental goals.⁹ (Figure 2).

⁷,"Main country data and directions for 2019-2022". Ministry of finance of Georgia. 2018 <https://www.mof.ge/5177>

⁸The author's research on the example of Shida Kartli region in Georgia; 2022

⁹Eka Datuashvili. 2020. „Social entrepreneurship in Georgia. Institute of Civil Society” ©. Tbilisi. pp. 2-11.

Figure 2

Commissioned by the "Center for Strategic Research and Development of Georgia (CSR DG)" by the "Institute of Social Research and Analysis" and with the support of the European Union for Georgia, the study "Research on the impact of social enterprises in Georgia" was conducted, the focus groups were interviewed: employees and beneficiaries of social enterprises/organizations providing social services and users

of social services and 143 social enterprises. According to the research, the majority of organizations consider themselves to be "self-identified" social enterprises and position themselves as social enterprises, one-third identify themselves with organizations providing social services. In this study, it is given in what ways social enterprises are financed. (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Please tell us which of the following sources was/are your main source of income during the last 4 years (2018-2021) that you used to fulfill the social objectives of the enterprise	Organization providing social services №=74	Social enterprise №=69	Organizations/enterprises/business companies participating in research №=143
	96		
Grants from local donors	15,6	19,2	17,3
Grants from international donors	17,7	16	16,9
Individual donations	11,3	12	11,7
Membership fee	-	2,4	1,1
State financing (voucher, etc.)	40,4	6,4	24,4
Donations of economic/business companies	5,7	1,6	3,8
Other	0,7	1,6	1,1

As it shows, state and donor organizations play a major role in providing financial support to Georgian enterprises. Individual donations and state sponsorships are also significant. Donor organizations actively provide financial support to social businesses. Because they have to pay attention to social needs as well, costs increase and mobilization of financial resources becomes difficult, unlike traditional businesses. So, donors play a big role in maintaining the sustainability of

a social enterprise. Based on the same research, it can be seen that the restrictions caused by the covid-19 pandemic have caused a lot of damage to the enterprises. Realization became difficult due to movement restrictions. For social enterprises, this factor turned out to be harmful. The percentage also clearly reflects (28.4%) the severity of the problem. (Table 2)

Table 2

What are the main reasons why your company did not make a financial profit during the pandemic (2020-21)	A provider of social services № 53	social enterprise №52	Organizations/enterprises/business companies participating in the research № 86
	96		
Limited access/non-existence of modern technologies	7,9	3,2	5,3
Taxes imposed by the state (including tax penalties)	1,3	3,2	2,3
Unqualified/unmotivated employees	1,3	3,2	2,3
Management's existing problems/challenges	6,6	5,3	5,8
Infrastructural failure of the enterprise	5,3	5,3	5,3
Interruption of the active operation of the enterprise as a result of the restrictions caused by the Covid-19 pandemic	44,7	36,8	40,4
Difficulties in selling manufactured products	9,2	28,4	19,9
Increased competition	3,9	4,2	4,1
Other	19,7	10,5	14,6

For the largest part of representatives of social enterprises (15.1%), the main motivation was to create an equal, safe environment for vulnerable groups of society and to improve their quality of life. 26.1% of respondents in social entrepreneurs name wider recognition of the importance of social enterprises (13.1%) and promotion of social reintegration of vulnerable groups (13.1%) as a motivation factor. For 9.3%, it was important to expand the direction of entrepreneurial activity. 18.4% of representatives of organizations providing social services state that it is most important for them to provide necessary services to vulnerable groups (first of all, disabled people). And 16.7% name the creation of an equal and safe environment for the vulnerable groups of the society and improvement of their quality of life as the main motivation. 16.1% of respondents representing organizations providing social services emphasize the promotion of an inclusive social environment, and 12.8% - promote of social reintegration of representatives of vulnerable groups.

Research Results

The study of the issues showed that the development of social business is important to ensure equality and a safe environment in the country. This activity needs proper promotion and support. Social business is facing various challenges and problems. This is especially noticeable in the example of developing countries, including Georgia. For the development of social business, this topic still lacks the recognition and support of a large-scale society. One of the reasons for this is that social business is not recognized at the legal and political level. The customer desires to create a common identifying brand for social business representatives, for the product to have a distinguishing mark. People are willing to buy a social business product if they know that it is made by them. In the example of several countries, the separation of social business into a separate field of activity has increased the awareness and sales of these business objects.

Conclusion

Therefore, as the research and its review showed, social business activities require innovative approaches, maintaining a balance between income and social, and environmental goals. Taking into account the challenges is necessary for the normal functioning of the organization. One of the main challenges is to maintain a balance between meeting public needs and economic profit. In general, this is the goal of social business and entrepreneurship. Finding an unmet social need in the market and using good commercial opportunities play a big role in maintaining this balance. It is possible to be motivated to solve social problems but not consider the economic aspect. The next challenge is choosing a strategy. A weak strategy can cause problems for a business with a good idea. In this case, lack of knowledge, incorrect planning, and not knowing where to seek financial support; It might become a problem. The reason for choosing a weak or wrong strategy can be time, opportunities, and hybridity of activities. In order for social business to be able to realize its goals, the state should play an active role in the development of social enterprises. It is possible to be motivated to solve social problems but not consider the economic aspect. The next challenge is choosing a strategy. It is important to find donors and support them. As a result, we will get profitable enterprises, a healthy environment, and the welfare of society.

References

1. Muhammad Yunus. „Building Social Business: The New Kind of Capitalism that Serves Humanity's Most Pressing Needs Paperback” – May 10, 2011, by Muhammad Yunus. www.yunusssb.com
2. Rangan, V. Kasturi, and Katharine Lee. January 2016. "Grameen Danone Foods Ltd., a Social Business." Harvard Business School Case 511-025
3. Top Social Impact Startups in Korea You Need to Know. June 13, 2022. www.seoulz.com
4. Flash Eurobarometer 513 Social entrepreneurship and youth – October 2022, Summary. <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer>

5. "Main country data and directions for 2019-2022". Ministry of Finance of Georgia. 2018 <https://www.mof.ge/5177>

6. Eka Datuashvili. 2020. Social entrepreneurship in Georgia. Institute of Civil Society ©. Tbilisi. pdf. pp. 2-11.

7. Alliance of Social Enterprises of Georgia <https://seageorgia.ge/ka/social-enterprises/10> 20.06. 2023

8. Research on the impact of social enterprises in Georgia, Tbilisi, 2022. Commissioned by the "Institute of Social Research and Analysis" and the "Center for Strategic Research and Development of Georgia (CSRDG)" p.137,139, 180, 181. Pdf. Social_Entrepreneurship_Research.pdf (civilin.org) 20.06. 2023